

Date Accessed (of search)	Search (Search term used)	Origin of website (e.g. Knowledge of Researcher; found in X documentation)	(Primary) Website	Website TYPE 1	Website TYPE 2 (i.e. Field Health)	High level finding (data we are interested in)	National; Regional or Cantonal	Experts Identified	Experts Note	New Website Identified	Website TYPE 1	Website TYPE 2 (i.e. Field Health)	Note	New Website Identified - Used as search?
02.02.2018	http://www.gov.scot/Resource/Doc/319441/0102105.pdf	SNF project	http://www.gov.scot/Resource/Doc/319441/0102105.pdf	Government website (National)	-	Getting it Right for Young Carers The Young Carers Strategy for Scotland 2010-2015 (July 2010) - It will build on the support already in place and take forward the recommendations of the landmark report, Care 21: The Future of Unpaid Care in Scotland. Caring Together sets out 10 key actions to improve support to carers over the next five years. The focus is on improved identification of carers, assessment, information and advice, health and wellbeing, carer support, participation and partnership. We are also pleased to have produced Getting it Right for Young Carers, which we believe will result in better outcomes for young carers. To the best of our knowledge, it is the first ever national young carers' strategy in Europe.	National (Scotland)	-	-	1. The Scottish Executive, 2005: The Care 21 Report: the Future of Unpaid Care in Scotland http://www.scotland.gov.uk/Publications/2006/02/28094157/0	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	We are also pleased to have produced Getting it Right for Young Carers, which we believe will result in better outcomes for young carers. To the best of our knowledge, it is the first ever national young carers' strategy in Europe.	-
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Scottish Government: Getting it Right for Every Child http://www.scotland.gov.uk/Topics/People/Young-People/childrenewelfare/girfec	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	-	y
02.02.2018	http://www.scotland.gov.uk/Publications/2006/02/28094157/0	http://www.gov.scot/Resource/Doc/319441/0102105.pdf	http://www.scotland.gov.uk/Publications/2006/02/28094157/0	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	The recommendations of a research project on the future of unpaid care in Scotland [2006]	National (Scotland)	-	-	http://www.gov.scot/Publications/2006/02/28094157/0	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	-	y
02.02.2018	http://www.gov.scot/Publications/2006/02/28094157/8	http://www.scotland.gov.uk/Publications/2006/02/28094157/0	http://www.gov.scot/Publications/2006/02/28094157/8	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	Annex One: Policy and context - the story so far: Annex One: Policy and context - the story so far 34 The starting point for the development of a Carers Strategy in Scotland was the UK Strategy, 'Caring for Carers', launched in February 1999. The UK Strategy heralded, for the first time in the UK, a substantial policy package for unpaid carers and it put carers' issues firmly on the political map. This was despite the fact that the first real legislative rights for carers, primarily the right of 'regular and substantial' carers to have their needs assessed as part of an assessment of the overall needs of the person being cared for, had been put in place under the UK-wide Carers (Recognition and Services) Act 1995. Implementation of the 1995 Act was patchy throughout the UK and given low priority, in Scotland primarily because of the sizeable impact at that time of local government reorganisation.	National (Scotland)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
02.02.2018	Scottish Government: Getting it Right for Every Child http://www.scotland.gov.uk/Topics/People/Young-People/childrenewelfare/girfec	http://www.gov.scot/Resource/Doc/319441/0102105.pdf	Scottish Government: Getting it Right for Every Child http://www.scotland.gov.uk/Topics/People/Young-People/childrenewelfare/girfec	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	Getting it right for every child (GIRFEC): GIRFEC is the national approach in Scotland to improving outcomes and supporting the wellbeing of our children and young people by offering the right help at the right time from the right people. It supports them and their parent(s) to work in partnership with the services that can help them.	National (Scotland)	-	-	http://www.gov.scot/Topics/People/Young-People/gettingitright/publications/girfec-policy-update-July-2017	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	Policy update - July 2017 Updated information on delivering the Getting it right for every child policy. This update replaces the policy document issued in September 2016.	-
02.02.2018	http://www.gov.scot/Topics/People/Young-People/gettingitright/publications/girfec-policy-update-July-2017	http://www.scotland.gov.uk/Topics/People/Young-People/childrenewelfare/girfec	http://www.gov.scot/Topics/People/Young-People/gettingitright/publications/girfec-policy-update-July-2017	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	Getting it right for every child Policy update July 2017: Policy update to replace the September 2016 policy update	National (Scotland)	-	-	http://www.gov.scot/Resource/0052/00529614.pdf	Government website (National)	PDF	-	-
02.02.2018	http://www.gov.scot/Resource/0052/00529614.pdf	http://www.scotland.gov.uk/Topics/People/Young-People/gettingitright/publications/girfec-policy-update-July-2017	http://www.gov.scot/Resource/0052/00529614.pdf	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	1. Policy Update July 2017 Delivering the Getting it right for every child 1. Purpose 1.1 The purpose of this document is to provide updated information on delivering the Getting it right for every child policy and replace the policy document issued in September 2016. The document includes information on: • Parts 4 and 5 of the Children and Young People (Scotland) Act 2014 and the Supreme Court judgment. • The Children and Young People (Information Sharing) (Scotland) Bill •	National (Scotland)	-	-	-	-	-	Search terms: Children and Young People (Scotland) Act 2014 and the Supreme Court judgmentXXThe United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC) mentioned	-
06.02.2018	young carers legislation scotland	-	http://www.gov.scot/Topics/Health/Support-Social-Care/Unpaid-Carers/implementation/Carers	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	The Carers (Scotland) Act 2016 will take effect from April 1, 2018.	National (Scotland)	-	-	http://www.legislation.gov.uk/asp/2016/9/contents	UK Government website (National)	Government website (National)	The Carers (Scotland) Act 2016 will take effect from April 1, 2018.	websites about consultation completed
06.02.2018	http://www.legislation.gov.uk/asp/2016/9/contents	http://www.gov.scot/Topics/Health/Support-Social-Care/Unpaid-Carers/implementation/Carers-scotland-act-2016	http://www.legislation.gov.uk/asp/2016/9/contents	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	PART 1 KEY DEFINITIONS; PART 2 ADULT CARER SUPPORT PLANS AND YOUNG CARER STATEMENTS; PART 3 PROVISION OF SUPPORT TO CARERS; PART 4 CARER INVOLVEMENT; PART 5 LOCAL CARER STRATEGIES; PART 6 INFORMATION AND ADVICE FOR CARERS; PART 7 GENERAL PROVISION; PART 8 FINAL PROVISIONS; SCHEDULECONSEQUENTIAL MODIFICATIONS	National (Scotland)	-	-	http://www.legislation.gov.uk/asp/2016/9/pdfs/asp_20160009_en.pdf	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	Changes to legislation:Carers (Scotland) Act 2016 is up to date with all changes known to be in force on or before 02 February 2018. There are changes that may be brought into force at a future date. Help about Changes to Legislation	-

06.02.2018	http://www.legislation.gov.uk/asp/2016/9/pdfs/asp_20160009_en.pdf	http://www.legislation.gov.uk/asp/2016/9/contents	p_20160009_en.pdf	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	The Bill for this Act of the Scottish Parliament was passed by the Parliament on 4 February 2016 and received Royal Assent on 9th March 2016 An Act of the Scottish Parliament to make provision about carers, including the identification of carers' needs for support through adult carer support plans and young carer statements; the provision of support to carers; the enabling of carer involvement in certain services; the preparation of local carer strategies; the establishment of information and advice services for carers; and for connected purposes.	National (Scotland)	-	-	-	-	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	-	-
06.02.2018	-	-	-	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	2 Meaning of "young carer" In this Act "young carer" means a carer who— (a) is under 18 years old, or (b) has attained the age of 18 years while a pupil at a school, and has since attaining that age remained a pupil at that or another school. 3 Meaning of "adult carer" In this Act "adult carer" means a carer who is at least 18 years old but is not a young carer. ; CHAPTER 2 YOUNG CARER STATEMENTS Duty to prepare young carer statement 12 Duty to prepare young carer statement (1) In this Act a "young carer statement" means a statement prepared by a responsible authority setting out— (a) a young carer's identified personal outcomes, (b) a young carer's identified needs (if any), and (c) the support (if any) to be provided by the responsible local authority to a young carer to meet those needs.	National (Scotland)	-	-	-	-	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	Definition of a young carer (and a carer) , CHAPTER 2 YOUNG CARER STATEMENTS Duty to prepare a young carers statement	-
06.02.2018	http://www.parliament.scot/parliamentarybusiness/Bills/86987.aspx	http://www.gov.scot/Topics/Health/Support-Social-Care/Unpaid-Carers/Implementation/Carers-scotland-act-2016	http://www.parliament.scot/parliamentarybusiness/Bills/86987.aspx	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	A Bill for an Act of the Scottish Parliament to make provision about carers, including the identification of carers' needs for support through adult carer support plans and young carer statements; the provision of support to carers; the enabling of carer involvement in certain services; the preparation of local carer strategies; the establishment of information and advice services for carers; and for connected purposes. Current Status of the Bill This Scottish Government Bill was introduced by Shona Robison MSP, Cabinet Secretary for Health, Wellbeing and Sport on 9 March 2015 and was passed by the Parliament on 4 February 2016	National (Scotland)	Shona Robison MSP,	Cabinet Secretary for Health, Wellbeing and Sport	http://www.parliament.scot/S4/Bills/Carers%20(Scotland)%20Bill/b61s4-introd-en.pdf	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	CARERS (SCOTLAND) BILL ----- EXPLANATORY NOTES (AND OTHER ACCOMPANYING DOCUMENTS)	y	
06.02.2018	http://www.parliament.scot/S4/Bills/Carers%20(Scotland)%20Bill/b61s4-introd-en.pdf	http://www.parliament.scot/parliamentarybusiness/Bills/86987.aspx	http://www.parliament.scot/S4/Bills/Carers%20(Scotland)%20Bill/b61s4-introd-en.pdf	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	These documents relate to the Carers (Scotland) Bill (SP Bill 61) as introduced in the Scottish CARERS (SCOTLAND) BILL ----- EXPLANATORY NOTES (AND OTHER ACCOMPANYING DOCUMENTS)	National (Scotland)	-	-	-	-	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	-	-
06.02.2018	http://www.parliament.scot/ResearchBriefingsAndFactsheets/S4/SB_15-24_Carers_Scotland_Bill.pdf	http://www.parliament.scot/parliamentarybusiness/Bills/86987.aspx	http://www.parliament.scot/ResearchBriefingsAndFactsheets/S4/SB_15-24_Carers_Scotland_Bill.pdf	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	SPICE Briefing Carers (Scotland) Bill: May 2015: The Carers (Scotland) Bill sets out a range of measures intended to improve the support given to carers. This includes the introduction of new duties on local authorities to support carers who are assessed as needing support and who meet eligibility criteria. This briefing sets out the Bill's main provisions and the response to these proposals from the Health and Sport Committee's call for written evidence. : Bill Proposals The Bill would remove the requirement for the care to be 'substantial' and 'regular' and; The Bill would define a young carer as a person under the age of 18 years, or a person who is 18 years but is still at school. An adult carer would be anyone else aged at least 18 years old.	National (Scotland)	Kathleen Robson and Nicola Hudson	Authors of SPICE Briefing Carers (Scotland) Bill: Scottish Parliament Information Centre (SPICE) Briefings are compiled for the benefit of the Members of the Parliament and their personal staff. Authors are available to discuss the contents of these papers with MSPs and their staff	-	-	-	-	-	
06.02.2018	http://www.parliament.scot/S4/Bills/Carers%20(Scotland)%20Bill/b61s4-introd-pm.pdf	http://www.parliament.scot/parliamentarybusiness/Bills/86987.aspx	http://www.parliament.scot/S4/Bills/Carers%20(Scotland)%20Bill/b61s4-introd-pm.pdf	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	This document relates to the Carers (Scotland) Bill (SP Bill 61) as introduced in the Scottish Parliament on 9 March 2015 SP Bill 61—PM 1 Session 4 (2015) CARERS (SCOTLAND) BILL -----	National (Scotland)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
06.02.2018	young carers policy scotland	-	http://www.gov.scot/Topics/Health/Support-Social-Care/Unpaid-Carers/ProgrammesandInitiatives/NationalStrategy	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	POLICY MEMORANDUM The Caring Together: The Carers Strategy for Scotland 2010 - 2015 and Getting it Right for Young Carers: The Young Carers Strategy for Scotland 2010 - 2015 set out a range of key actions, including a focus on: better identification of carers information and advice health and wellbeing carer support participation and partnership	National (Scotland)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	

06.02.2018	young carers policy scotland	-	http://www.gov.scot/Publications/2010/08/16095043/1	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	<p>Getting It Right For Young Carers: The Young Carers Strategy for Scotland: 2010 - 2015 Summary: The Scottish Government and the Convention of Scottish Local Authorities (who represent the 32 local councils in Scotland) have worked together to produce a new strategy for those of you who are young carers.</p> <p>The strategy is called Getting It Right For Young Carers. This booklet provides a summary of the strategy's main points.</p>	National (Scotland)	-	-	-	-	-	-	Getting It Right For Young Carers highlights the importance of recognising the rights that all children and young people have under the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC). We know that the demands that you face can sometimes deny you your UNCRC rights. In particular, the right: <p>to be protected from discrimination (article 2) to form and express your own views (article 12) to life, survival and healthy development (article 6) to spend time with friends (article 15) to enjoy opportunities for leisure and to relax and play (article 31) to education (article 28 and 29)</p>	#####
06.02.2018	young carers policy scotland	-	http://www.gov.scot/Publications/2017/03/2478	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	<p>Young carers: Review of research and data Wednesday, March 8, 2017 ISBN: 9781786528292</p> <p>This paper discusses the data and evidence on young carers and young adult carers. It combines an analysis of data on young carers from Scotland's Census 2011 with the findings of a review of the evidence on young carers focused on the period 2005-2015. The report is based on an SGSSS internship project undertaken by Nicola Benbow from the University of Stirling: Executive Summary This paper discusses the data and evidence on young carers and young adult carers. It combines an analysis of data on young carers from Scotland's Census 2011 with the findings of a review of the evidence on young carers focused on the period 2005-2015.</p> <p>The aim was to provide an increased understanding of the existing evidence on the prevalence and impacts of young</p>	-	Alex Rosenberg	socialresearch@gov.scot	-	-	-	-	-	-
06.02.2018	young carers policy scotland	-	https://news.gov.scot/news/more-support-for-young-carers	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	<p>September 2017: A new Young Carer Grant – worth £300 a year – will be part of a new package of support for young carers, First Minister Nicola Sturgeon announced today on a visit to the Edinburgh Young Carers Project. : For the purposes of the Young Carer Grant, a young carer is someone with caring responsibilities aged 16 to 17, or 18 and still at school.</p> <p>Work to further help young carers through the Young Scot National Entitlement Card will start in April 2018 and the scheme will be rolled out from April 2019. This will be followed by the Young Carer Grant in autumn 2019. Following pilot studies to examine technical options, free bus travel will be implemented in 2020-2021. : Carer's Allowance is awarded to all carers aged 16 and over who carry out at least 35 hours of caring a week.</p> <p>Today's announcement complements the commitment to increase Carer's Allowance in line with Jobseeker's Allowance. This will come into effect next summer and be backdated to</p>	-	-	-	-	-	-	NEW HELP : for young carers through the Young Scot National Entitlement Card will start in April 2018 and the scheme will be rolled out from April 2019. This will be followed by the Young Carer Grant in autumn 2019 . Following pilot studies to examine technical options, free bus travel will be implemented in 2020-2021 .	E20N20D20:O2 D20:O20N20 D20:O20C20:O 20N20D20:O20 B20:O20N20D2 O:O20A20:O20	
06.02.2018	young carers policy scotland	-	http://www.careinfoscotland.scot/topics/young-carers-and-young-adult-carers/caring-together-and-getting-it-right-for-young-carers/	Government website (National) ?	Social care	<p>This is the first ever national young carers' strategy in Europe. The Scottish Government is committed to making sure young carers aren't in inappropriate caring roles, and they're supported to be children and young people first and foremost. The strategy after 2015 The strategy is due for review in 2015. (May 2017)</p>	National (Scotland)	-	-	http://www.gov.scot/Publications/2010/08/16095043/1	-	-	-	-	-
06.02.2018	young carers policy scotland	-	https://professionals.carers.org/scottish-government-guidance/current-guidance-young-carers-schools-scotland	NGO	Carer organisations	<p>The Education (Additional Support for Learning) (Scotland) Act 2004 and 2009 introduces a framework for providing for children and young people who require additional support with their learning for any reason.</p> <p>'Getting It Right for Young Carers' The Young Carers Strategy for Scotland 2010 -2015 sets out action points to be implemented through local authority education services to support young carers in schools.</p> <p>Education Maintenance Allowance is payable to eligible 16-19 year olds in Scotland.</p>	National (Scotland)	-	-	http://www.emascotland.com/admindocuments.cfm	Government website (National) ?	Education	Lots more in depth information	n	
06.02.2018	young carers policy scotland	-	https://carers.org/country/carers-trust-scotland	NGO	Carer organisations	<p>Carers Trust Scotland is the largest provider of comprehensive carers support services in Scotland. There are at least 759,000 carers aged 16 and over in Scotland and 29,000 young carers. The value of care provided by carers in Scotland is £10,347,400,000 a year.</p> <p>Three out of five of us will become carers at some stage in our lives and 1 in 10 of us is already fulfilling some sort of caring role.</p>	National (Scotland)	-	-	https://carers.org/EPYC	NGO	Carer organisations	-	y	

06.02.2018	https://carers.org/EPYC	https://carers.org/country/carers-trust-scotland	https://carers.org/EPYC	NGO	Carer organisations	EPYC Project : Thanks to funding provided by the European Commission through the Erasmus+ programme, a group of organisations from Germany, Scotland, Ireland, Italy and Austria are working to find new ways to support young carers.	National (Scotland)	Louise Morgan Paul Traynor	Carers Trust Scotland, Young Carers Development Manager Working with the SYCSA – lmorgan@carers.org : Carers Trust Scotland, Policy and Campaigns Officer (Young and Young Adult Carers) – ptraynor@carers.org	http://www.ep-yc.org/	NGO	?	ERASMUS Project	n
06.02.2018	young carers policy scotland	-	https://carers.org/article/policy-and-legislation-scotland	NGO	Carer organisations	The primary law that affects carers in Scotland is called the Carers (Scotland) Act. It will be implemented from April 2018 and will replace parts of existing legislation that supports unpaid carers. The Act will make it simpler for carers to be identified as needing support with their caring role, and will make getting this support easier too. Carers' assessments will be known as Adult Carer Support Plans (for adults) and Young Carer Statements (for young carers under 18). Both of these will focus more on how the caring role is affecting the person, rather than the number of hours spent caring. : Young Carer Statements (for young carers under 18). : The Scottish Government has set up a number of working groups to take forward the development of regulations and guidance, leading up to the implementation of the Act in April 2018. The groups are made up of different stakeholders, including carers, and will be chaired by Scottish Government officials. Groups will then feed back to the Carers Act Implementation Steering Group.	National (Scotland)	-	number of working groups to take forward the development of regulations and guidance	https://professionals.carers.org/policy-and-legislation-scotland	NGO	?	-	y
06.02.2018	https://professionals.carers.org/policy-and-legislation-scotland	https://carers.org/article/policy-and-legislation-scotland	https://professionals.carers.org/policy-and-legislation-scotland	NGO	Carer organisations	The Carers (Scotland) Bill was published on 9 March 2015. We will be working closely with the Scottish Government, MSPs and other decision-makers, carers and Network Partners to make sure the Bill can make a real difference for carers and carers' services Scotland has a Carers' Strategy - Caring Together: The Carers Strategy for Scotland 2010-2015. Carers Trust Scotland has produced a guide for carers on Self-directed support. In October 2013, at the second Carers' Parliament, Alex Salmond announced the Scottish Government's intention to legislate for carers before the Scottish General Election in 2016.	National (Scotland)	-	-	https://www.gov.uk/guidance/equality-act-2010-guidance	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	Relationship between UK and Scottish Law for carers	y
06.02.2018	https://www.gov.uk/guidance/equality-act-2010-guidance	https://professionals.carers.org/policy-and-legislation-scotland	https://www.gov.uk/guidance/equality-act-2010-guidance	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	The Equality Act 2010 legally protects people from discrimination in the workplace and in wider society. It replaced previous anti-discrimination laws with a single Act, making the law easier to understand and strengthening protection in some situations. It sets out the different ways in which it's unlawful to treat someone. Find out more about who is protected from discrimination, the types of discrimination under the law and what action you can take if you feel you've been unfairly discriminated against.	National (Scotland)	-	-	https://www.gov.uk/discrimination-on-your-rights	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	New website: Who is protected by Equality Act	n
06.02.2018	young carers policy scotland	-	http://www.gov.scot/Resource/Doc/319441/0102105.pdf	Government website (National)	Government website (National)		National (Scotland)	-	-	-	-	-	-	#WERT!
06.02.2018	young carers policy scotland	-	https://www.mygov.scot/young-carer-support/	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	Young carers: support Last updated: 5 February 2018 If you're a young carer (under 18) or a young adult carer (aged 18 to 25), you can get help, advice and support.	National (Scotland)	-	-	http://www.careinfoscotland.scot/topics/young-carers-and-young-adult-carers/	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	New website: Information for young and young adult carers	n
06.02.2018	young carers policy scotland	-	https://childreninscotland.org.uk/how-can-we-support-young-carers-in-education-settings/	NGO	Children and young people	I'm really pleased that over the past 15 years the profile of young carers in Scotland has risen and been kept to the fore. This has happened first through the national strategy for young carers, Getting It Right for Young Carers, and the Carers Act (Scotland) 2016. The Act will be implemented in April 2017. [elsewhere 2018] All of this has been achieved through consultation with young carers.	National (Scotland)	Louise Morgan	Co-ordinator for the Scottish Young Carers Services Alliance	-	-	-	-	-

06.02.2018	young carers policy scotland	-	https://www.disabilityrightsuk.org/news/2017/sep-tember/more-support-young-carers-scotland	NGO	Disability	<p>Young Carer Grant : The grant will be awarded, from autumn 2019, to young carers aged 16 to 18 who do at least 16 hours of caring a week and who are still at school.</p> <p>This is part of a full package of support for Scottish carers, including:</p> <p>increased Carer's Allowance in line with Jobseeker's Allowance from summer 2018, backdated to April 2018.</p> <p>the right for young carers to a get statement from a local authority, setting out their circumstances and support needs, from 1 April 2018.</p> <p>a Young Scot National Entitlement Card giving non-cash benefits to young carers aged 11-18, which will be rolled out from April 2019.</p> <p>free bus travel for those on Young Carer Grant starting 2020-2021.</p> <p>planned increases for families supporting more than one disabled child.</p>	National (Scotland)	-	-	https://news.gov.scot/news/more-support-for-young-carers	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	-	
06.02.2018	young carers policy scotland	-	https://young.scot/young-carers/	NGO	Youth organisations	Young Carers: Find out how to apply for Carer's Allowance	National (Scotland)	-	-	https://young.scot/information/rights/apply-for-carers-allowance/	NGO	Youth organisations	-	y
06.02.2018	https://young.scot/information/rights/apply-for-carers-allowance/	https://young.scot/young-carers/	https://young.scot/information/rights/apply-for-carers-allowance/	NGO	Youth organisations	Young adult carers can get Carers Allowance if they are aged 16 or over and care for someone 35 hours per week	National (Scotland)	-	-	https://young.scot/information/rights/carers-act/	NGO	Youth organisations	Applies to carers living in Scotland, England and Wales	y
06.02.2018	https://young.scot/information/rights/carers-act/	https://young.scot/information/rights/apply-for-carers-allowance/	https://young.scot/information/rights/carers-act/	NGO	Youth organisations	EASY HEADLINES about The Carers Act 2016 (Scotland) The Carers (Scotland) Act 2016 will come into force on the 1st April 2018. Find out how it might affect you if you are a young carer.	National (Scotland)	-	-	-	-	-	several links from this site	n
06.02.2018	young carers legal provisions scotland	-	http://www.gov.scot/Publications/2002/08/15306/10474	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	<p>Legal entitlement to services and government commitment to provision</p> <p>Young carers are entitled to support from local and health authorities under legislation contained in the Children Act 1989, the Children (Scotland) Act 1995 and the Carers (Recognition and Services) Act 1995. Since April 1990 the UK Government and Scottish Executive have expanded the support available to all carers, including young carers.</p> <p>The Carers (Recognition and Services) Act 1995 emphasises the idea of service support for carers and has generally widened the range and reach of support for informal carers. However, the Act has been criticised for not incorporating a commitment to ongoing resources. In many cases services for carers have been withdrawn or cut because of the financial pressures on local authorities, potentially leaving the rights of all carers seriously compromised. Carers National Association 1997, Still Battling? The Carers Act one year on, Carers National</p>	National (Scotland)	-	several researchers cited here	-	-	-	Old page 2002	n
06.02.2018	young carers legal provisions scotland	-	http://www.gov.scot/Publications/2002/08/15306/10473	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	YOUNG CARERS: ASSESSMENT AND SERVICES	National (Scotland)	-	several researchers cited here	-	-	-	Old page 2003	n
06.02.2018	young carers legal provisions scotland	-	https://professionals.carers.org/sites/default/files/young_carers_summary_briefing.pdf	NGO	Carer organisations	<p>Young carers and the Carers (Scotland) Bill</p> <p>The Carers (Scotland) Bill was introduced to the Scottish Parliament in March 2015. This Bill is specifically for unpaid carers and will consolidate existing rights from other pieces of legislation as well as enshrining new rights in law.</p> <p>There are specific provisions in the Bill for young carers around assessment (the Young Carers Statement) and involvement in care and support planning. Most of the Bill applies to all carers including young carers, and information about the Bill in general is available on https://professionals.carers.org/policy-and-legislation-scotland#carersbill</p> <p>The Bill will modify Sections 24 and 24A of the Children (Scotland) Act 1995, and replace it with a section in the Carers (Scotland) Bill.</p> <p>The Scottish Government have estimated that there are around 44,000 young carers in Scotland.</p> <p>This is an increase from the number of young carers identified through the Census in 2011 and is based on Scottish Health Survey data.</p>	National (Scotland)	Heather Noller	Carers Trust Scotland hnoller@carers.org / 07827 914634	-	-	-	How the Bill modifies old legislation: The Bill will modify Sections 24 and 24A of the Children (Scotland) Act 1995, and replace it with a section in the Carers (Scotland) Bill.	
06.02.2018	young carers legal provisions scotland	-	https://www.carersuk.org/help-and-advice/practical-support/getting-care-and-support/young-carers-and-carers-of-children-under-18	NGO	Carer organisations	<p>Young carers and carers of children under 18</p> <p>Young carers and carers of children under 18 have different assessments to adult carers of adults: The information in this section applies to people living in England. If you live in Wales, Scotland or Northern Ireland, please click the relevant link below. [LINKS to all UK countries]</p>	-	-	-	https://www.carersuk.org/images/Factsheets/Factsheet_51020_Assessments_-_guide_to_getting_help.pdf	NGO	Carer organisations	-	